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**Fauna and taxonomy of
Dolichopodidae (Diptera)**

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Фауна и таксономия хищных мух Dolichopodidae (Diptera). Сборник научных работ. Под редакцией И.Я. Гричанова и О.П. Негрובה. Санкт-Петербург: ВИЗР РАСХН, 2013. 96 с. (Приложение к журналу «Вестник защиты растений»).

Fauna and taxonomy of Dolichopodidae (Diptera). Collection of papers. Igor Ya. Grichanov & Oleg P. Negrobov, editors. St.Petersburg: VIZR RAAS, 2013. 96 p. («Plant Protection News, Supplement»).

Сборник включает обзорные статьи по фауне и таксономии хищных мух-зеленушек семейства Dolichopodidae. Описаны новые виды, приведены новые указания для видов из Палеарктической, Ориентальной и Афротропической зоогеографических областей. Составлены региональные определители видов из родов *Asyndetus* и *Syntormon*. Впервые составлен справочный список 52 родов, 735 видов и подвидов семейства Dolichopodidae, отмеченных на территории Российской Федерации. Сборник будет полезен специалистам – энтомологам и экологам, интересующимся энтомофагами, студентам и аспирантам учебных и научных учреждений.

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AFROTROPICAL SPECIES OF THE GENUS *ASYNDETUS* LOEW (DIPTERA: DOLICHOPODIDAE) WITH NOTES ON SOME PALAEARCTIC AND ORIENTAL SPECIES

Igor Ya. Grichanov

All-Russian Institute of Plant Protection (VIZR), Podbelskogo 3, St. Petersburg, Pushkin, 196608, Russia. E-mail: grichanov@mail.ru

The genus *Asyndetus* Loew, 1869 in the Afrotropical Region is reviewed. It comprises 14 species including five new species and two doubtful species described by females. The genus is differentiated from other Diaphorinae by the following combination of characters: vein M broken and displaced; upper part of proepisternum with 1–4 fine setae; acrostichals present, biserial; male segment 8 with strong projecting setae. New species *A. congensis* sp. n. from D.R. Congo, *A. savannensis* sp. n. from D.R. Congo and Senegal, *A. madagascarensis* sp. n. from Madagascar, *A. namibiensis* sp. n. from Namibia and *A. pseudoseparatus* sp. n. from Gambia are described. A key to the Afrotropical species of *Asyndetus* is provided, as well as new records for some Afrotropical, Palearctic and Oriental species. Lectotype and paralectotypes are designated for *A. albipalpus* Loew, 1871.

KEY WORDS: Dolichopodidae, *Asyndetus*, Afrotropical, Palearctic, India, new species, new records, key.

И.Я. Гричанов. Виды рода *Asyndetus* Loew (Diptera: Dolichopodidae) тропической Африки с заметками о некоторых палеарктических и ориентальных видах

Дан обзор афротропических видов рода *Asyndetus* Loew, 1869, который содержит 14 видов, включая пять новых для науки и два сомнительных вида, описанных по самкам. Род отличается от других родов подсемейства Diaphorinae следующими признаками: жилка крыла M в вершинной части с разрывом; проэпистернум с 1–4 щетинками в верхней части; акростихальные щетинки двурядные; 8-й сегмент брюшка с крепкими длинными щетинками. Описаны и иллюстрированы *A. congensis* sp. n. из Д.Р. Конго, *A. savannensis* sp. n. из Д.Р. Конго и Сенегала, *A. madagascarensis* sp. n. с Мадагаскара, *A. namibiensis* sp. n. из Намибии, *A. pseudoseparatus* sp. n. из Гамбии. Приведены определитель афротропических видов *Asyndetus* и новые указания для известных видов из тропической Африки, Индии и Палеарктики. Обозначены лектотип и паралектотипы для *A. albipalpus* Loew, 1871.

Всероссийский научно-исследовательский институт защиты растений (ВИЗР), шоссе Подбельского, 3, Санкт-Петербург, Пушкин, 196608, Россия.

Introduction

The genus *Asyndetus* Loew, 1869 belongs to the subfamily Diaphorinae. There are more than 100 species of the genus (Grichanov, 2003–2013) reported from all zoogeographical regions of the Earth. In the Old World, it is quite diverse in the tropical and subtropical belts. Negrobov (1973) published the last review of Palearctic *Asyndetus* species. Subsequently Bickel (1996) redescribed the genus, and Grootaert & Meuffels (2002) defined the *A. latifrons* species group. Oriental and Australasian faunas of the genus were treated by Meuffels & Grootaert (1993), Grootaert & Meuffels (2002), Bickel (1996), Zhang & Yang (2003), Wang et al. (2007).

Curran (1926a, b) was the first who described *Asyndetus* species from the Afrotropical Region (three species from South Africa). Few data, including descriptions of new species, have subsequently been published on the genus. Parent (1929a, 1930, 1937) and Séguy (1950) described 5 new species from DR Congo, Madagascar, Niger and the Hala'ib Triangle region. Grichanov (2000, 2012) found the South African *A. virgatus* Curran in Namibia and Sierra Leone; the Madagascan *A. decaryi* Parent was

recorded from South Africa (Grichanov & Urban, 2009) and Kenya (Grichanov et al., 2011a). *A. latifrons* (Loew) widely distributed in the Palearctic and Oriental Regions was firstly reported from the Afrotropics (Gabon) by Grichanov (2011). There were no suitable keys to the Afrotropical species.

Material and methods

The holotypes and paratypes of the new species and other material cited are housed at the All-Russian Institute of Plant Protection, St. Petersburg, Russia (VIZR), the Finnish Museum of Natural History, Helsinki, Finland (MZH), the Hungarian Natural History Museum, Budapest, Hungary (HNHM), the Museum of Zoology, Lund University, Lund, Sweden (MZLU), the Natal Museum, Pietermaritzburg, South Africa (NMSA), the National Museum, Bloemfontein, South Africa (BMSA), the National Museum of Natural History, Paris, France (MNHN), the Natural History Museum, London, United Kingdom (BMNH), the Natural History Museum of Denmark (ZMUC), the Naturhistoriska Riksmuseet, Stockholm, Sweden (NHRS), the Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences, Brussels, Belgium (IRSNB), the Royal Museum for Central Africa, Tervuren, Belgium (RMCA), the Zoological Institute of the Russian Academy of Sciences, St. Petersburg (ZIN), the Zoological Museum of Moscow State University, Russia (ZMU), the Zoological Museum of Tel-Aviv University, Israel (TAU), and the Zoologisches Museum, Universität Kiel, Kiel, Germany (ZMUK).

Specimens were studied and illustrated with a ZEISS Discovery V–12 stereomicroscope and an AxioCam MRc5 camera. Morphological terminology and abbreviations follow Cumming & Wood (2009). The relative lengths of the podomeres should be regarded as representative ratios and not measurements. Body length is measured from the base of the antenna to the tip of abdominal segment 8. Wing length is measured from the base to the wing apex. Male genitalia were macerated in 10% KOH. Figures showing the male genitalia in lateral view are oriented as they appear on the intact specimen, with the morphologically ventral surface of the genitalia facing up, dorsal surface down, anterior end facing right and posterior end facing left. Information on world distribution for known species follows Grichanov (2003–2013).

Systematics

**Family Dolichopodidae
Subfamily Diaphorinae
Genus *Asyndetus* Loew**

Asyndetus Loew, 1869: 34. Type species: *Asyndetus ammophilus* Loew, 1869, by designation of Coquillett, 1910: 511.

Meringopherusa Becker, 1902: 56; Strobl, in Czerny, Strobl, 1909: 189. Type species: *Meringopherusa separata* Becker, 1902, by designation of Dyte, 1975: 247.

Diagnosis. This cosmopolitan genus is defined (together with *Cryptophleps* Lichtwardt, 1898) by the synapomorphy of the broken and displaced vein M which readily distinguishes it from the related and probably ancestral genus *Diaphorus* Meigen, 1824. Small to medium-sized flies (body length 1.5–4.5 mm); upper part of proepisternum with 1–4 fine setae; acrostichals present, biserial; male segment 8 with four strong projecting setae (Grichanov, 2011). A thorough re-description of all the characters can be found in Bickel (1996). See also the definition of *A. latifrons* species

group by Grootaert & Meuffels (2002).

Remarks. The closely related genus *Cryptophleps* was originally distinguished from *Asyndetus* by lacking wing cross-vein *dm-cu* (Lichtwardt, 1898), and was later distinguished from *Asyndetus* by lacking mesonotal acrostichal setae (Lamb, 1922; Parent, 1938), hypopygial macrochetæ (Negrobov, 1973; Grootaert & Meuffels, 1987) or upper proepisternal setae (Bickel 2005), by reduced number of notopleural and supraalar setae (Negrobov, 1973). All these characters are quite variable within the *Asyndetus*, *Cryptophleps* and other genera of Diaphorinae, correlating mainly to the size of species. By now the presence or absence of acrostichal setae is the only appropriate character for distinguishing the two genera (Capellari & Grichanov, 2012).

Composition. The genus numbers more than 100 mostly Holarctic species, widely distributed across arid zones of Palaearctic and Afrotropical Regions. Thirteen species are recorded from Afrotropical Region.

Review of Afrotropical species

Asyndetus albifacies Parent, 1929a: 46.

Type material examined: Paratypes: 2♂, M. Halaib, 21.I.[19]29 / Coll. Efflatoun, Egypte / *Asyndetus albifacies* Par. ♂, cotype / paratype [MNHN].

Material examined: 1♂, Saudi Arabia: Bahara, March 77, Dr. Buttiker / 7 [BMNH]; 1♂, 2♀, Saudi Arabien, W. Buttiker / Bahara, 24.3.76 [BMNH]; 1♂, Saudi Arabien, W. Buttiker / Selouly's Farm, 30.10.75 [BMNH]; 2♂, Israel: Eilat env., ~29.57°N, 34.97°E, 25.X.2011, N. Vikhrev [ZMU].

Distribution: Type locality: Mt. Halaib. Afrotropical: Hala'ib Triangle (Egypt–Sudan border); Palaearctic: Israel, Saudi Arabia. New for Israel and Saudi Arabia.

Asyndetus albifrons Parent, 1929a: 45.

Type material examined: Paratypes: 2♂, 2♀, Bir Agrab, South Eastern Desert, 3.III.1928 / Coll. Efflatoun, Egypte / *Asyndetus albifrons* Par. ♂, cotype / paratype [MNHN]; 1♀, same labels [RMCA].

Distribution: Type locality: Bir Agrab (South Eastern Desert). Palaearctic or Afrotropical: Egypt (close to Hala'ib Triangle); Palaearctic: Iraq.

Asyndetus amaphinius Séguy, 1950: 275.

Type material examined: Holotype ♂: Monts Tarraouaji, 900 m, 8-12-IX / IFAN-1947, L. Chopard, A. Villiers / Type [red label] / *Asyndetus amaphinius* Type, E. Séguy vid. 48 [MNHN].

Distribution: Type locality: Niger: Aïr, Monts Tarraouaji. Afrotropical: Niger.

Asyndetus crassitarsis Curran, 1926b: 410.

Distribution: Type locality: South Africa: Transvaal, Kaapmuiden. Afrotropical: South Africa.

Asyndetus decaryi Parent, 1929b: 187 (in key); 1930: 100 (description).

Type material examined: Holotype ♂: Madagascar: Prov. d'Ananalava, Maromandia, B. Decary, 1922 / Type [red label] / *Asyndetus decaryi* n. sp. ♂, O. Parent det. [MNHN].

Material examined: 3♂, 3♀, South Africa: Cape Province, 10 km S of Koomlanskloof, 32°40'S, 19°02'E, Malaise-trap, marshy meadow at riverside, 5-7.X.1994, M. Söderlund

[ZMLU]; 1♂, RSA: Cape Prov. 9 km NW Worcester, 33°37'S, 19°22'E, 9.X.1994, Loc. 11, leg. R. Danielsson [ZMLU]; 1♂, South Africa: Cape Province, Umngazi Mouth, 3129Da, 20.X.1972, M.E. Irwin, 3 to 10 m, coastal dunes [NMSA]; 1♂ (in alcohol), Madagascar: Foulpointe, 2.XI.1991, A. Pauly col., plage, bac jaune [IRSNB]; 2♂ (in alcohol), Madagascar: Foulpointe, X.1993, A. Pauly col., forêt, lagune, Piège Malaise [IRSNB]; 6♂, 2♀ (in alcohol), Madagascar: Tam., Foulpointe, 2.XI.1991, A. Pauly col., plage [IRSNB]; 3♂ (in alcohol), Madagascar: 25 km W. Morarano-chrome, XI.1991, forêt, bac jaune, A. Pauly [IRSNB]; 2♂ (in alcohol), Madagascar: Manakambahiny, Atn., I.1991, A. Pauly [IRSNB].

Distribution: Type locality: Madagascar: province d'Ananalava, Maromandia. Afrotropical: Kenya, Madagascar, South Africa.

Asyndetus latifrons (Loew), 1857: 46 (*Diaphorus*); Loew, 1869: 298 (*Asyndetus*); Negrobov: 1973: 165 (Fig. 25); Pärvu, 1995: 298 (Fig. 5); Grootaert & Meuffels, 2002: 43 (Fig. 7); Grichanov et al., 2011b: 26 (Fig. 8), 33 (Fig. 78).

Material examined: Afrotropical: 1♂, 1♀, Kenya: Mombasa, 13.VIII.1983, A. Freidberg [TAU]; 1♂, [DR Congo:] Congo-belge, Bambesa, 22.VIII.1938, J. Vrydagh [IRSNB]; 1♂, (in alcohol), Gabon: Kougouleu, IX.1984, A. Pauly, Piège Malaise [IRSNB]; 4♂, 4♀ (in alcohol), Gabon: Voleu-Ntem, Assok-Ngum, 21.II.1986, A. Pauly, bac jaune, coupe forestière [IRSNB]; 38♂♀ (in alcohol), Gabon: Libreville, IX.1984, A. Pauly [IRSNB]; 16♂♀ (in alcohol), Gabon: Owendo, 9.XII.1985, A. Pauly, dunes littorales, bacs jaune [IRSNB]; Palaearctic: 1♂, [Russia:] Krasnodar Territory, Arkhipo-Osipovka, 14-26.VI.1992 / peach orchard, Grichanov; 1♂, Krasnodar Terr., Gelendzhik, env. vill. Betta, stream r. Betta, on stones, 11.VII.2006, Volfov, Talashinskii [VIZR]; 1♀, Russia: N Osetia-Alania, Alagir env., 5.VII.2000, I. Grichanov [VIZR]; 1♀, Russia: Adygea, Maikop, Vostochnaya str., garden, 4.IX.2009, K. Tomkovich [ZMU]; 2♂, 1♂, [Russia:] Belgorod Region, Borisovka vil., 5.VII.2001, D.D. Kostrov [ZMU]; 1♂ [size 3 mm], Yemasoyia Riv., Cyprus, coll. G. Mavromoustakis, 13.7.56 / R.I.Sc.N.B. 24236, Coll. M. Bequart [IRSNB]; 1♀, Turkey: Adapazari reg., Karasu env., 27.VIII.2009, N. Vikhrev, N. Dvoret'skaya [ZMU]; 1♂, Turkey: Zonguldak reg., Alapli env., 41.14°N, 31.36°E, 19-20.VI.2010, N. Vikhrev [ZMU].

Distribution: Type locality: Poland: "Schlesien". Afrotropical: DR Congo, Gabon, Kenya; Palaearctic: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Czech, Estonia, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, N Kazakhstan, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Russia (Adygea, Krasnodar, Leningrad, N Osetia-Alania, Voronezh, S Ural), Slovakia, Spain, Syria, Turkey; Oriental: Bangladesh, China, India, Pakistan, Philippines, Thailand. New for Kenya, DR Congo, Cyprus, some Russian regions (Adygea, Belgorod, N Osetia-Alania).

Asyndetus virgatus Curran, 1926a: 34; Grichanov, 2012: 2 (Figs. 1–2)

Type material examined: Holotype ♂, Paratype ♂: Middelburg [25°47'S:29°28'E], 13.2.[19]25, H.K. Munro [NMSA]; Paratype 1♀: East London, 9.3.25, H.K. Munro [NMSA].

Material examined. 2♂, Natal: Weenen, IV.1924, H.P. Thomasset / Pres. by Imp. Inst. Ent. Brit. Mus. 1932-338 / *Asyndetus virgatus* Curr., det. C.E. Dyte; 1♀, Natal: Weenen, 2840 ft., I.1924, H.P. Thomasset, Thorn country [other labels are the same; BMNH]; 2♂, 3♀, **South Africa:** Natal, Ashburton, 15 km SE of Pietermaritzburg,

II.1977, J.G.H. Londt, Malaise in Grassland [NMSA]; 1♂, **South Africa**: Natal, Lynnfield Park, 13 km SE of Pietermaritzburg, 29°41'S, 30°29'E, Acacia thornveld area, 31.III.1989, A.E. Wittington [NMSA]; 1♂, **South Africa**: Natal, 15 km SE Ingwavuma, 2732Aa, 21.II.1979, J.G.H. Londt, Bushy area with big trees ex Malaise trap [NMSA]; 1♂, **South Africa**: KwaZulu-Natal, Royal Natal National Park, Mahai River, 28°41.386'S, 28°56.288'E, 17–18.II.2010, Malaise trap (1), straddling Mahai River, A.H. Kirk-Spriggs [BMSA]; 25♂♀, **South Africa**: Free State, Brandfort, Florisbad Res. Stat., 28°46.039'S, 26°04.234'E, 4–6.IV.2009, Malaise traps, Acacia savanna, A.H. Kirk-Spriggs [BMSA]; 1♂, **South Africa**: KwaZulu-Natal, Ndumo Game Reserve, Shokwe area, 26°52.125'S, 32°13.731'E, 30.XI–4.XII.2009, Malaise traps, Ficus forest, A.H. Kirk-Spriggs [BMSA]; 1♀, **South Africa**: KwaZulu-Natal, Ndumo Game Reserve, main road, 26°54.288'S, 32°17.974'E, 4–8.XII.2009, Malaise traps, sand [forest] & broad-leaved deciduous forest, A.H. Kirk-Spriggs [BMSA]; 1♀, **South Africa**: E. Cape, Tsitsikamma National Park, Plaatbos Nature Reserve, 33°59.283'S, 23°55.275'E, 20–22.I.2009, Malaise trap, Oubrug, Storms River margin, indigenous forest, A.H. Kirk-Spriggs & S. Otto [BMSA]; 8♂, 8♀ [in alcohol], [Ivory Coast:] C.I., Komandimi, NP Comoé, Camp Univ. Würzb., 8°45' N, 3°49' W, G-Schale, 13-31.I.1998, leg. S.Hilger [ZMUK]; 2♂, 1♀ (in alcohol), Gabon: Ntoun, X.1984, A. Pauly, Piège Malaise, Pâturage [IRSNB]; 2♀ (in alcohol), Gabon: Booué, IX.1984, A. Pauly, Piège Malaise [IRSNB]; 5♂, (in alcohol), Gabon: Ntoun, X.1985, A. Pauly, , bac jaune, plantation sur brûlis [IRSNB], 36♂♀ (in alcohol), Gabon: Lastourville, VIII-X.1984, A. Pauly, Piège Malaise [IRSNB]; 4♂, 5♀ (in alcohol), Guinea-Bissau: Bafatá, Bafatá, 8-10.IX.2004, N. Jönsson [ZIN]; 1♂, [DR Congo:] Congo-belge, Rutshuru, 30.XI.1937, J. Ghesquière [IRSNB]; 1♂, [DR Congo:] Congo-belge, Kivu, Rutshuru (riv. Fuku), 1250 m, 6.VII.1935, G.F. de Witte: 1682 [IRSNB]; 1♂, [DR Congo:] Congo Belge, P.N.G., Miss. H. De Saeger, II/gd/4, 24.VII.1952, H. De Saeger, 3864 [RMCA]; 1♂, [DR Congo:] Congo Belge, P.N.G., Miss. H. De Saeger, II/gd/4, 18.IX.1952, H. De Saeger, 4077 [RMCA]; 1♂, [DR Congo:] Congo Belge, P.N.G., Miss. H. De Saeger, II/gd/8, 10.IV.1952, H. De Saeger, 3313 [RMCA]; 1♂, [DR Congo:] Congo Belge, P.N.G., Miss. H. De Saeger, II/fd/17, 3.I.1952, H. De Saeger, 2991 [RMCA]; 1♂, Kenya: Tiwi, Beaches, 4 14 S, 39 36 E, 14-23.VIII.1975, B. Petersen [ZMUC]; 1♂, Ghana: Kumasi, No. 13, 18-20.VI.1965, leg. Endrody-Younga [HNHM]; 1♂, Botswana: SE district, Gaborone city, National Museum garden, light trap, 8-10.XI.1993, Bert A.V. Viklund [NHRS]; 1♂, Malawi: Kasungu Nat. Park, Lifupa Camp, 1333Aa, 9-10.XII.1980, 1000 m, Stuckenberg & Londt, *Brachystegia* [NMSA]; 1♂, 1♀, Yemen: Ma'rib, Ma'rib, 24.IV.1992, R. Linnavuori [MZH].

Remarks: A male from Yemen differs in the presence of 6 strong bristles (rather than 4) on segment 8 and elongate setulae on anteroventral and anterodorsal surfaces of hind tibia, about as long as diameter of tibia. Surstyli of studied specimens are variable to a certain extent in length and setulation.

Distribution: Type locality: South Africa: Mpumalanga: Middelburg. Afrotropical: Botswana, DR Congo, Kenya, Gabon, Ghana, Guinea-Bissau, Ivory Coast, Malawi, Namibia, Sierra Leone, South Africa, Yemen. New for Botswana, DR Congo, Kenya, Gabon, Ghana, Guinea-Bissau, Ivory Coast, Malawi, and Yemen.

Asyndetus pseudoseparatus sp. nov.

(Fig. 1)

Diagnosis. *A. pseudoseparatus* differs from other Afrotropical species of the genus in lacking cross-vein *dm-cu*, distinctly broken M_{1+2} , simple tarsi bearing claws and small pulvilli. It is very close to *A. separatus* in external morphology, differing from the latter in the presence of claws and small pulvilli on at least anterior four tarsi, in absence of strong ventral setae on mid and hind femora. *A. separatus* male has enlarged tarsal pulvilli, about half as long as segment 5, lacking claws on fore and mid tarsi and having one claw on hind tarsus. Male genitalia of the two species are very close to each other except for the shorter mid-dorsal seta on ventral lobe of surstylus in *A. separatus*, half as long as figured for *A. pseudoseparatus* (Fig. 1). In addition, an examined *A. separatus* male from Egypt has asymmetrical epandrial lobes (see below).

Type material. **HOLOTYPE** ♂, **Gambia:** Kotu stream about 3 km SW Bakau, in vegetation and fresh water, 23.II.1977, UTM 28PCK16-88, Loc. No. 3 / Lund Univ., Syst. Dept., Sweden Gambia/Senegal. Febr.-March 1977, Cederholm - Danielsson - Larsson - Mirestrom - Norling - Samuelsson [ZMLU]. **PARATYPES:** 1 ♀, same labels; 1 ♀, Gambia: about 1 km E Yoga Jula milestone 105, 2.III.1977, Loc. No. 13, UTM 28PDK28-83 / Lund Univ., Syst. Dept., Sweden Gambia/Senegal. Febr.-March 1977, Cederholm - Danielsson - Larsson - Mirestrom - Norling - Samuelsson [ZMLU].

Etymology. The species is named for its similarity with *Asyndetus separatus* Becker.

Description. Male: Head: frons bronze-black, grey pollinose; face black, densely whitish pollinose, weakly narrowed, slightly higher than wide under antennae; occiput concave, black, grey pollinose; pair of long ocellar, pair of long vertical, and pair of shorter postvertical bristles; postocular setae relatively short, uniserial, black above, whitish below; lower postcranium with rather long white setae; eyes with microscopic white hairs. Antennae inserted in middle of head, black, longer than height of head; scape long, bare; pedicel covered with dorsal and ventral setulae; postpedicel subtriangular, with rounded apex, as long as high, covered with short hairs; arista-like stylus mid-dorsal, with microscopic hairs; length ratio of scape to pedicel to postpedicel to stylus, 9/4/6/26. Palpus short, yellow, with several hairs and 2 black apical setae; proboscis short, black, with short black hairs.

Thorax: mesonotum metallic dark-green; pleura black-green, weakly pollinose; four pairs of dorsocentral bristles; acrostichals biserial, well developed, 4 or 5 pairs; scutellum with two long strong setae and two short lateral hairs.

Legs: coxae and femora black except yellow apices, tibiae yellow, fore and mid tarsi black except most part of basitarsus yellow, hind tibia dark at apex, hind tarsus entirely black; fore coxa anteriorly with black hairs and setae of various length; mid coxa with black setae anteriorly and apically; mid and hind coxae with black external seta; fore femur with short setulae; mid and hind femora with 3 to 5 fine ventral hairs, 2/3 as long as femora diameter and 2 or 3 fine subapical anterior setae; fore tibia without conspicuous setae; mid tibia with 2 long anterodorsal, 2 short posterodorsal bristles; hind tibia with 1 or 2 anterodorsal, 3-4 posterodorsal bristles; all tibiae with apical setae; tarsi simple, with short claws and small pulvilli; coxa, femur, tibia and tarsomere (from first to fifth) length ratio: fore leg: 25/38/39/20/9/7/5/5, mid leg: 18/40/47/25/10/8/5/5, hind leg: 12/45/56/15/14/9/6/-.

Fig. 1. *Asyndetus pseudoseparatus* sp. nov., hypopygium, lateral aspect.

Wing: hyaline, veins brown; R_1 short, ending at basal 2/5 of wing; ratio of costal section between R_{2+3} and R_{4+5} to that between R_{4+5} and M_{1+2} , 14/23. R_{2+3} and R_{4+5} straight; M_{1+2} distinctly interrupted with broken sections partly running parallel to each other; cross-vein *dm-cu* absent; anal vein well developed; anal angle obtuse; lower calypter yellow, with fine white cilia; halter yellow.

Abdomen: bronze-black, with black hairs and marginal setae; sterna 4-5 developed, setose; tergum 6 glabrous; sternum 6 and segment 7 reduced; segment 8 large, rounded, with four strong black bristles; hypopygium (Fig. 1) black, small, partly concealed; epandrium flattened laterally, with left lateral foramen; hypandrium fused with epandrium, simple, short; phallus long and thin, simple; a pair of long and broad symmetrical epandrial lobes originating near base of hypandrium, with 2 apical and 1 basal setae as figured; surstylus bilobate, more or less straight; ventral lobe of surstylus gradually narrowed towards apex, bearing some short setulae and one strong middorsal seta; dorsal lobe narrow, more than half as long as ventral lobe, bearing short apical spine; postgonite narrow, slightly curved ventrally, reaching middle of surstylus; cercus small, rounded, bearing short setae.

Female: similar to male except lacking MSSC.

Measurements (mm): Body length 1.7, antenna length 0.5, wing length 1.7, wing width 0.6.

Asyndetus congensis sp. nov.

(Figs. 2–6)

Diagnosis. The new species is close to *A. namibiensis*, both differing from other Afrotropical species in the unusually ciliated hind tibia (see key below). Male of *A. congensis* has ventral setae on mid and hind femora about twice as long as diameter of corresponding femur.

Type material. HOLOTYPE ♂, D.R. Congo, Oriental Prov., Lieki village area at: 00°41.117'N, 24°14.362'E, 25.v–4.vi.2010, A.H. Kirk-Spriggs, sweeping, bush paths & village environs [BMSA]. PARATYPE ♀, same label.

Etymology. The species is named for the country of origin.

Description. **Male** (Fig. 2): **Head** (Fig. 3): vertex flat; upper occiput concave; frons wider than face, black, grey pollinose; face wide, parallel-sided and covered by silvery-white shining dust on black ground-colour; face under antenna 1.5 times as wide as basal height of postpedicel; one pair of strong ocellars; one strong vertical bristle on each side at eye margin; one postvertical on each side, not far from upper postocular

seta; postocular setae relatively short, uniserial, black above, whitish below; lower postocranium with rather long white setae. Antenna (Fig. 3) black; scape and pedicel normal; postpedicel subtriangular with rounded tip, nearly as long as high, bearing short hairs; arista-like stylus dorsal, with short segment 1 and long segment 2. Length ratio of scape to pedicel to postpedicel to stylus (segments 1 and 2), 8/6/8/5/58. Proboscis and palpus small, black; palpus whitish pollinose, with black setae.

Figs. 2–5. *Asyndetus congensis* sp. nov.: 2 – habitus, 3 – head, 4 – hind leg, 5 – wing.

Thorax: shining greenish-black, weakly pollinose; upper part of proepisternum with one black seta anteriorly; lower part of proepisternum with one strong and one weak black setae above coxa; 4 pairs of strong dorsocentral bristles of about equal length; additional short fine seta between 2nd and 3rd dorsocentrals, somewhat shifted; short acrostichals in biserial row; scutellum with one pair of strong widely spaced bristles and two small lateral setae.

Legs: mainly greenish-black, with black bristles and hairs, fore and mid knees dirty yellow, fore and mid tibiae pale brown; fore and mid coxae with some short and long setae anteriorly; hind coxa with one seta at base; fore femur with two ventral rows of fine setae, usually shorter than height of femur (MSSC); mid femur with 5-6 anteroventral and 5-6 posteroventral setae in middle, 2-3 times longer than height of femur (MSSC), with short anteroventrals and posteroventrals at apex; hind femur (Fig. 4) with 3-4 anteroventrals in middle and 3-4 posteroventrals behind middle, 1.5-2 times longer than height of femur (MSSC), with 2 elongate subapical anteroventral and 3 short subapical posteroventral setae; fore tibia with 1 fine dorsal at basal quarter, with 3-4 apicals and posteroventral row of elongate setulae (MSSC); mid tibia with 2 anterodorsals and 2 posterodorsals, of which upper anterodorsal bristle somewhat stronger, 3-4

apicals; hind tibia (Fig. 4) inconspicuously thickened in basal half (MSSC), with 2 strong dorsal and 1 strong posterodorsal bristles, with 3–4 shorter posterodorsals, with 7–8 fine posterior setae in basal two thirds, 1.5–2 times longer than diameter of tibia (MSSC), with double antero- and posterodorsal row of fine setae in distal two thirds, 1.5–2 times longer than diameter of tibia (MSSC), with 4 apicals; fore basitarsus with posteroventral row of elongate setulae, slightly longer than diameter of segment (MSSC); all tarsi without claws, with enlarged pulvilli (MSSC); femur, tibia and tarsomere (from first to fifth) length ratio: fore leg: 77/72/34/11/9/7/10, mid leg: 77/82/40/19/12/9/10, hind leg: 89/94/30/23/15/9/10.

Wing (Fig. 5): colorless and transparent, with brown veins; ratio of costal section between R_{2+3} and R_{4+5} to that between R_{4+5} and M_{1+2} , 23/34; R_{4+5} and M_{1+2} subparallel in middle part and slightly divergent in apical part of wing; M_{1+2} with bend in middle of apical part, strongly weakened at bend and somewhat weakened in apical part; section of M_{1+2} between posterior cross-vein (*dm-cu*) and bend slightly longer than that between bend and wing margin (69/66); *dm-cu* located at level of R_1 ; ratio of apical portion of CuA_1 to *dm-cu*, 73/13; anal vein distinct, anal lobe developed, anal angle obtuse; calyp-ter yellow, with simple yellow cilia; halter yellow.

Abdomen: black, with black setation; sterna 4–5 developed, setose; tergum 6 glabrous; sternum 6 and segment 7 reduced; segment 8 large, rounded, with four strong black bristles; hypopygium (Fig. 6) black, small, partly concealed; epandrium flattened laterally, with left lateral foramen; hypandrium fused with epandrium, simple, short, triangular (ventral aspect); phallus long and thin, simple; a pair of long and narrow symmetrical epandrial lobes originating near base of hypandrium, pointed at apex, with 3–4 setae as figured; surstylus bilobate, more or less straight; ventral lobe of surstylus subtriangular in basal half, narrow in distal half, with subapical ventral notch, bearing some short setulae and one strong but short middorsal seta; dorsal lobe narrow, half as long as ventral lobe, bearing short apical seta; postgonite reduced, concealed; cercus black, small, rounded, bearing short setae.

Fig. 6. *Asyndetus congensis* sp. nov., hypopygium, lateral aspect.

Female: similar to male except lacking MSSC, otherwise as noted: face white pollinose; hind tibia with 1 anterodorsal and 2–3 posterodorsal bristles; abdomen with anal plate projecting, rounded; hemitergites of last segment each with 4 thick spines.

Measurements (mm): Body length 2.1, antenna length 0.76, wing length 2.2, wing width 0.8.

Asyndetus savannensis sp. nov.

(Figs. 7–9)

Diagnosis. The new species is close to *A. congensis* and *A. madagascarensis*, differing in distinctly interrupted M_{1+2} , with broken sections usually partly running parallel to each other; in acicular in distal half epandrial lobe, bearing one strong apical seta. *A. congensis* and *A. madagascarensis* have more or less weakened bend in middle of apical part M_{1+2} ; epandrial lobe bearing two apical setae in *A. madagascarensis*; male of *A. congensis* has ventral setae on mid and hind femora about twice as long as diameter of corresponding femur (see key below).

Type material. **HOLOTYPE** ♂, [D.R. Congo:], Congo Belge, P.N.G., Miss. H. De Saeger, II/fd/17, 29.VII.1952, H. De Saeger, 3844 [RMCA]. **PARATYPES** 9♂, same label; 1♂, [D.R. Congo:], Congo Belge, P.N.G., Miss. H. De Saeger, II/gd/4, 8.VIII.1952, H. De Saeger, 3923 [RMCA]; 1♂, [D.R. Congo:], Congo Belge, P.N.G., Miss. H. De Saeger, II/gd/6, 2.IX.1952, H. De Saeger, 4023 [RMCA]; 1♂, [D.R. Congo:], Congo Belge, P.N.G., Miss. H. De Saeger, II/gc/8, 9.IX.1952, H. De Saeger, 4042 [RMCA]; 1♂, [D.R. Congo:], Congo Belge, P.N.G., Miss. H. De Saeger, II/gd/4, 31.VII.1952, H. De Saeger, 3859 [RMCA]; 1♂, [D.R. Congo:], Congo Belge, P.N.G., Miss. H. De Saeger, II/gd/4, 25.VIII.1952, H. De Saeger, 3978 [RMCA]; 2♂, Senegal: M'Bour, St. ORSTOM, 7.XII.1979, D. Pluot [MNHN].

Etymology. The species is named for the ecoregion uniting two rather distant collection areas in NE Congo and Senegal, where the new species was taken.

Description. Similar to *A. congensis* in all respects, except for the following features. **Male: Head:** antenna (Fig. 7) black; length ratio of scape to pedicel to postpedicel to stylus (segments 1 and 2), 10/6/10/5/61.

Thorax: no additional short seta between 2nd and 3rd strong dorsocentrals.

Figs. 7–8. *Asyndetus savannensis* sp. nov.: 7 – antenna, 8 – wing.

Legs: mainly greenish-black, knees dirty yellow, fore and mid tibiae and bases of tarsi pale brown, hind tibia brown; all femora with two ventral rows of fine setae, half as long as height of femur (MSSC); hind tibia simple, without rows of remarkable setae; femur, tibia and tarsomere (from first to fifth) length ratio: fore leg: 86/82/40/17/12/10/11, mid leg: 92/96/47/22/15/10/10, hind leg: 95/105/34/26/15/10/13.

Wing (Fig. 8): colorless and transparent, with brown veins; ratio of costal section between R_{2+3} and R_{4+5} to that between R_{4+5} and M_{1+2} , 28/46; R_{4+5} distinctly convex anteriorly at wing apex; M_{1+2} distinctly interrupted, with broken sections usually partly running parallel to each other; section of M_{1+2} between posterior cross-vein (*dm-cu*) and bend distinctly longer than that between bend and wing margin (88/72); *dm-cu* located right before level of R_1 ; ratio of apical portion of CuA_1 to *dm-cu*, 93/18.

Abdomen: black, with black setation; sterna 4–5 developed, setose; tergum 6 glabrous; sternum 6 and segment 7 reduced; segment 8 large, rounded, with four strong black bristles; hypopygium (Fig. 9) black, small, partly concealed; epandrium flattened laterally, with left lateral foramen; hypandrium fused with epandrium, simple, short, triangular (ventral aspect), with apical brush of setae; phallus long and thin, practically

simple, with indistinct dorsal serration at base of swollen part; a pair of long symmetrical epandrial lobes originating near base of hypandrium, broad at base, acicular at apex (with somewhat variable length and width, in holotype slightly longer, than in some paratypes), with 1 apical and 2 subapical setae as figured (variable in location and length in paratypes); surstylus bilobate, more or less straight; ventral lobe of surstylus subtriangular in basal half, narrow in distal half, with subapical ventral notch, bearing some short setulae (variable in number and length in paratypes) and one short, but strong apicoventral spine, having no middorsal seta; dorsal lobe narrow, about half as wide as ventral lobe in middle, bearing short apical spine; postgonite bilobed, with both lobes narrow, curved ventrally, reaching apex of dorsal lobe of surstylus; cercus black, small, rounded, bearing short setae.

Fig. 9. *Asyndetus savannensis* sp. nov., hypopygium, lateral aspect.

Female: unknown.

Measurements (mm): Body length 2.6–2.8, antenna length 0.85, wing length 2.6, wing width 0.9.

***Asyndetus namibiensis* sp. nov.**

(Figs. 10–12)

Diagnosis. The new species is close to *A. congensis*, both differing from other Afrotropical species in the unusually ciliated hind tibia (see key below). Male of *A. namibiensis* differs in ventral setae on mid and hind femora about half as long as diameter of corresponding femur.

Type material. **HOLOTYPE** ♂ [in glycerol in vial, mounted on pin], Namibia: Katima Mulilo Dist., mopane in Salambala, M4, S17°42'55" E24°32'47", 24–26.II.2001, E. Marais & A.H. Kirk-Spriggs, yellow pans [BMSA]. **PARATYPES** 4♂, 4♀ [in alcohol in vial, 1♂, 1♀ dried and mounted on pins], same label [BMSA].

Etymology. The species is named for the country of origin.

Description. Similar to *A. congensis* in all respects, except for the following features. (All specimens are quite discoloured due to long-term storage in alcohol, with major bristles brown to brown-black.). **Male: Head:** antenna (Fig. 10) with postpedicel trapezoidal, with rounded tip, 1.3 times as long (along ventral margin) as high at base, bearing short hairs; arista-like stylus basodorsal; palpus discoloured, but apparently dark, brownish in dried specimen. Length ratio of scape to pedicel to postpedicel to stylus (segments 1 and 2), 12/11/20/8/39.

Figs. 10–12. *Asyndetus namibiensis* sp. nov., 10 – antenna, 11 – hind leg, 12 – hypopygium, lateral aspect.

Thorax: upper part of proepisternum with one seta; lower part of proepisternum with one strong and one weak setae above coxa; 4 pairs of strong dorsocentral bristles of about equal length; no additional seta between 2nd and 3rd dorsocentrals; short acrostichals in biserial row; scutellum with one pair of strong bristles and two small lateral setae.

Legs: discoloured, with coxae and femora distinctly darker than tibiae; femora without strong bristles, with short anteroventrals and posteroventrals at apex; hind femur (Fig. 11) with one strong erect ventral seta at basal third, not longer than height of femur (MSSC); fore tibia with 3–4 apicals; mid tibia with 2 anterodorsals and 1–2 posterodorsals, of which upper anterodorsal bristle somewhat stronger, 3–4 apicals; hind tibia (Fig. 11) with 1–2 posterodorsals, with one dorsal and one ventral rows of elongate semi-erect setae in distal half, of which ventral setae about as long as diameter of tibia (MSSC), with 4 apicals; all tarsi without claws, with enlarged pulvilli (MSSC); femur, tibia and tarsomere (from first to fifth) length ratio: fore leg: 80/76/43/18/13/8/10, mid leg: 90/96/51/23/17/10/9, hind leg: 90/104/34/27/20/13/10.

Wing: similar to that in *A. congensis*; ratio of costal section between R₂₊₃ and R₄₊₅ to that of costal section between R₄₊₅ and M₁₊₂, 26/39; section of M₁₊₂ between *dm-cu* and bend distinctly shorter than that between bend and wing margin (55/78); ratio of apical portion of CuA₁ to *dm-cu*, 74/14.

Abdomen: tergum 6 almost glabrous, with at most 2 middorsal setae; segment 7 reduced; segment 8 with four strong bristles and short hairs; the bristles nearly as long as epandrium; hypopygium (Fig. 12) brown, small, partly concealed; phallus long and thin, simple; epandrial lobe subtriangular, pointed at apex, with three setae as figured; ventral lobe of surstylus elongate-triangular (dorso-lateral aspect), pointed at apex, bearing some short setulae and one strong middorsal seta; dorsal lobe narrow, rod-like, bearing weak apical seta; postgonite narrow, curved ventrally, reaching middle of surstylus; cercus small, rounded, bearing short setae.

Female: similar to male except lacking MSSC, otherwise as noted: postpedicel subtriangular with rounded tip, nearly as long as high; mid tibia with both anterodorsals equally strong; hind tibia with few short dorsal setae.

Measurements (mm): Body length 2.2 (dry) – 2.7 (in alcohol), antenna length 0.7, wing length 2.2, wing width 0.9.

Asyndetus madagascarensis sp. nov.

(Figs. 13–15)

Diagnosis. The new species is close to *A. virgatus*, differing in longer postpedicel, nearly 2 times longer than high, and presence of the large suboval epandrial lobe (see key below).

Type material. **HOLOTYPE** ♂ [in glycerol in vial, mounted on pin], **MADAGASCAR:** Fia[narantsoa Province], Ranomafana [National Park, 21°00'S 47°30'E], 19.I.1992, A. Pauly, forêt (IRSNB). **PARATYPES** 14♂, 7♀ [in alcohol in vial, 1♂, 1♀ dried and mounted on pins], same label [IRSNB].

Etymology. The species is named for the country of origin.

Description. Similar to *A. congensis* in all respects, except for the following features. (All specimens are quite discoloured due to long-term storage in alcohol, with major bristles brown to brown-black.). **Male: Head:** antenna (Fig. 13) with postpedicel large, trapezoidal, with rounded tip, 1.8 times as long (along ventral margin) as high at base, bearing short hairs; arista-like stylus basodorsal; palpus discoloured, but apparently dark, brownish in dried specimen. Length ratio of scape to pedicel to postpedicel to stylus (segments 1 and 2), 12/10/22/6/36.

Figs. 13–14. *Asyndetus madagascarensis* sp. nov.: 13 – antenna, 14 – wing.

Thorax: upper part of proepisternum with one seta; lower part of proepisternum with one strong and one weak setae above coxa; 5 pairs of strong dorsocentral bristles; short acrostichals in biserial row; scutellum with one pair of strong bristles and two small lateral setae.

Legs: discoloured, with coxae and femora distinctly darker than tibiae; all femora with double row of long ventral setae along entire length, at least half as long as height of femur, in addition to subapical ventral bristles (MSSC); at apices those setae nearly as long as height of corresponding femur; fore tibia with 3–4 apicals; mid tibia with 2 anterodorsals and 2 posterodorsals, of which upper anterodorsal bristle somewhat stronger, 3–4 apicals; hind tibia with one dorsal row of about 8 short setae, of which one middorsal seta strongest, slightly longer than diameter of tibia (MSSC), with 4 apicals; all tarsi without claws, with enlarged pulvilli (MSSC); femur, tibia and tarsomere (from first to fifth) length ratio: fore leg: 75/71/37/14/10/6/9, mid leg: 84/80/42/17/11/8/8, hind leg: 88/98/27/22/14/9/8.

Wing (Fig. 14): similar to that in *A. congensis*; ratio of costal section between R_{2+3} and R_{4+5} to that of costal section between R_{4+5} and M_{1+2} , 27/37; wing vein *dm-cu* faint, located before level of R_1 ; section of M_{1+2} between *dm-cu* and bend distinctly longer than that between bend and wing margin (82/63); ratio of apical portion of CuA_1 to *dm-*

cu, 89/9.

Abdomen: tergum 6 glabrous; segment 7 reduced; segment 8 with four strong bristles and short hairs; hypopygium (Fig. 15) small, partly concealed; phallus long and thin, simple; epandrial lobe suboval, with three long setae as figured; ventral lobe of surstylus elongate-triangular (dorso-lateral aspect), acute at apex, bearing some short setulae and one or two strong middorsal setae; dorsal lobe narrow, rod-like, bearing short apical spine; postgonite narrow, curved ventrally, reaching middle of surstylus; cercus small, rounded, bearing moderately long setae.

Fig. 15. *Asyndetus madagascarensis* sp. nov. hypopygium, lateral aspect.

Female: similar to male except lacking MSSC, otherwise as noted: postpedicel subtriangular with acute tip, as long as high; mid tibia with both anterodorsals equally strong; hind tibia with 2 anterodorsal and about 5 short dorsal setae.

Measurements (mm): Body length 2.1 (dry) – 2.6 (in alcohol), antenna length 0.65, wing length 2.1, wing width 0.85.

Doubtful species

Asyndetus indifferens Curran, 1926b: 411.

Remarks: A female holotype (South African Museum, Cape Town, not seen) was incompletely described, being compared with a male of *A. crassitarsis* Curran, 1926b, differing from the latter in brown fore tibia, the character being common in females of *A. virgatus* (Curran, 1926a) and *A. decaryi* (Parent, 1929b). I think the *A. indifferens* may be conspecific to either *A. virgatus* or *A. decaryi*.

Distribution: Type locality: South Africa: Zululand, M'fongosi. Afrotropical: South Africa.

Asyndetus inermis Parent, 1937: 7.

Type material examined: ♀ [holo]type: [DR Congo:] Congo-belge, Rives Busira, VI.1936, J. Ghesquière / R. Mus. Hist. Nat. Belg. 10482 / *Asyndetus inermis* n.sp. ♀, O. Parent / O. Parent det. 1936: *Asyndetus inermis* n.sp. / tête disparue du course duretour du determinateur [RMCA].

Remarks: The holotype examined is strongly damaged. According to the original description, the species is close to the *A. albifrons* female, differing in reduced number of bristles on tibiae (1 antero-, 2 posterodorsals on mid tibia and 2 antero-, 2 posterodorsals on hind tibia in *A. inermis* vs. 2 antero-, 2 posterodorsals on mid tibia and 2 antero-, 4 posterodorsals on hind tibia in *A. albifrons* and all Afrotropical species of the genus)

and in distinctly interrupted wing vein M_{1+2} (weakly interrupted in distal part in *A. albifrons*). Legs black except fore and mid knees.

Distribution: Type locality: Congo-belge, Rives Busira. Afrotropical: DR Congo.

Key to Afrotropical species of *Asyndetus* based on male characters

Remarks: Females usually cannot be identified without males of the same series; *A. inermis* and *A. indifferens*, known only from females, are not included.

1. At least anterior four tarsi with claws, with small pulvilli; M_{1+2} distinctly interrupted with broken sections partly running parallel to each other; wing vein *dm-cu* indistinct; 1.7–2.2 mm *pseudoseparatus* **sp. n.**
– At least fore tarsus without claws, with enlarged pulvilli; M_{1+2} usually with bend in middle of apical part, more or less weakened at bend; wing vein *dm-cu* usually distinct 2
2. Fore basitarsus slender; segments 4–5 of fore tarsus dilated and flattened; 3 mm *crassitarsis* Curran
– Fore tarsus unmodified 3
3. Hind tarsus with claws, with small pulvilli; 2.5 mm *albifacies* Parent
– All tarsi without claws, with enlarged pulvilli 4
4. Hind tibia with ventral row of semi-erect setae, at least as long as diameter of tibia ... 5
– Hind tibia without remarkable ventral row of long setae 7
5. Hind tibia with regular or irregular row of elongate ventral or anteroventral setulae along entire length, not longer than diameter of tibia; epandrial lobe absent; 2.5–3 mm ...
..... *virgatus* Curran (see below)
– Hind tibia with regular ventral row of semi-erect setae in middle or in distal half, at least as long as diameter of tibia and distinctly longer than other setulae in the same and other rows; epandrial lobe well developed 6
6. Mid and hind femora with double rows of erect ventral setae, about 2 times longer than height of femur; epandrial lobe long and narrow; 2.1 mm *congensis* **sp. n.**
– Mid femur with ventral setae, at most as long as height of femur; hind femur ventrally almost bare, with one strong erect ventral seta at basal third, not longer than height of femur; epandrial lobe large, triangular; 2.2 mm *namibiensis* **sp. n.**
7. Mid and hind femora with double row of ventral setae along entire length, about half as long as diameter of femur, in addition to subapical ventral bristles; postgonite long and narrow 8
– Mid and hind femora with only subapical ventral bristles; postgonite usually short, concealed 10
8. M_{1+2} distinctly interrupted, with broken sections usually partly running parallel to each other; epandrial lobe pointed in distal half, long and narrow, bearing one strong apical seta *savannensis* **sp. n.**
– M_{1+2} with bend in middle of apical part, more or less weakened at bend; epandrial lobe either absent or bearing two apical setae 9
9. Postpedicel 1.5–2 times longer than high; wing vein *dm-cu* faint; epandrial lobe large, suboval, with three long setae; surstylus with dorsal lobe much narrower than ventral lobe; 2.1 mm *madagascarensis* **sp. n.**
– Postpedicel at most slightly longer than high; wing vein *dm-cu* strong; epandrial lobe absent; surstylus with dorsal lobe wide, nearly as wide as ventral lobe at apex; 2.5–3 mm *virgatus* Curran

10. Halter brown; M_{1+2} distinctly interrupted; hind tibia with 1 antero- and 1 posterodorsal bristles at base and one row of dorsal setae in distal half *amaphinius* Séguy
– Halter clear yellow; M_{1+2} usually with bend in middle of apical part, more or less weakened at bend; hind tibia differently setose 11
11. Section of M_{1+2} between posterior cross-vein (*dm-cu*) and bend about as long as that between bend and wing margin; epandrial lobe short and wide, distinctly shorter than surstylus, bearing two apical setae; 2–3 mm *latifrons* (Loew)
– Section of M_{1+2} between posterior cross-vein (*dm-cu*) and bend distinctly longer than that between bend and wing margin 12
12. Frons silvery-white pollinose; fore femur with double ventral row of long setae; 2.5 mm *albifrons* Parent
– Frons grey pollinose; fore femur with short setae; epandrial lobe long and slender, rod-like, bearing two apical setae; 2 mm *decaryi* Parent

Appendix. Notes on some Palearctic and Oriental species

General remarks: As noted above, the presence or absence of acrostichal setae is the only appropriate character for distinguishing *Asyndetus* from *Cryptophleps* (Capellari & Grichanov, 2012). Therefore, at least three Palearctic species described in the *Asyndetus* (*A. izius* Negrobov, 1973, *A. minutus* Negrobov et Shamshev, 1986 and *A. vividus* Negrobov et Shamshev, 1986) may be recombined with *Cryptophleps*. Nevertheless, my investigation of the hypopygial morphology of species of the two genera (see figures in this and cited papers) assumes that the genera will be synonymised in future.

Asyndetus albipalpus Loew, 1871: 295; Negrobov, 1973: 158.

Type material examined (here designated): Lectotype: ♂, [Uzbekistan: upper stream of Syr Darya River:] “Сыррь Дарья” [ZIN]. Paralectotypes: 2♂, same locality [ZIN].

Remarks: Describing new species from the A.P. Fedtshenko’s Turkistan expedition (1868–1871), H. Loew everywhere mentioned “Sarawschan Thal” (Zeravshan River Valley) as the type locality of his newly described species. Nevertheless, A.P. Fedtshenko collected the material from a much larger territory of the former Khanate of Kokand, from Kattaqurghon and Samarqand cities in the West to Fergana Valley and Alai Mountains in the East (e.g., Negrobov, 1981) within the present countries Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan and Uzbekistan. Some collection sites were also located in the present Kazakhstan. Most part of the identified material was returned to ZMU at the end of XIX century, while some voucher specimens (including Loew’s syntypes) were retained in the Natural History Museum, Berlin, Germany (MFN; Negrobov, 1981). A part of the ZMU material collected by Fedtshenko was probably borrowed or taken in exchange by A.A. Stackelberg (ZIN) before the WWII and was recently found in ZIN collection. It contains apparently mixture of identified and unidentified specimens under original labels, comprising locality number (separately) and brief description of a locality (in Cyrillic letters). Six specimens bear old hand-written museum labels with species names (including two specimens of Loew’s species with abbreviation “n. sp.”; one of the names is unpublished), followed by a more or less long row of unlabeled specimens. Some specimens bear hand-written (by Stackelberg) identification labels including types (with abbreviation “n. sp.”) of at least two species, i.e. the holotype of *Syntormon turanicus* Stackelberg, 1927 and two syntypes of *Teuchophorus rohdendorfi* Stackelberg, 1927, in addition to possible syntypes (with only locality labels) of *Fedtshenko-myia chrysotymoides* Stackelberg, 1927 and *Rhaphium turanicola* (Stackelberg, 1927).

Regarding *Asyndetus*, the ZIN old material examined comprises a series of specimens followed by a male (with broken abdomen) bearing an old hand-written museum label “*albipalpus* Lw.” and Stackelberg’s hand-written label “*Asyndetus albipalpis* Lw.”. The series contains three *Asyndetus* species, of which three males (with a locality label “Syr Darya” in Russian) fully correspond to the original Loew’s description of *A. albipalpus* (Loew, 1871) and generally correspond to a brief description of *A. albipalpus* by Negrobov (1973), which was based on Mongolian material and may belong to a different species. The other specimens belong to *A. longicornis* Negrobov, 1973 and *A. mixtus* Negrobov et Shamshev, 1986 (see below). Therefore, lectotype and paralectotypes are here designated to fix the current taxonomic concept of *A. albipalpus* and ensure consistent future interpretation.

Distribution: Type locality: Uzbekistan: upper stream of Syr Darya River (originally published as “Turkestan, Sarawschan Thal”). Palaeartic: ?Mongolia, Tajikistan, Uzbekistan.

Asyndetus barbiventris Stackelberg, 1952: 402; Negrobov, 1973: 159.

Material examined: 1♂, Tajikistan: Khatlon Prov., Farkhor distr., Novobod, 37.551°N, 69.460°E, 475 m asl, 6.VI.2010, water, pastures, K. Tomkovich [ZMU]; 1♂, [Kazakhstan or Uzbekistan]: Bairakum / 4 [pink label; ex coll. A.P. Fedtshenko 1871; ZIN];

Distribution: Type locality: Tajikistan: Tigrovaya balka, river Pyandzh, Kirovobod. Palaeartic: ?Kazakhstan, Tajikistan, ?Uzbekistan. First record after description.

Asyndetus chaetifemoratus Parent, 1925: 162.

Material examined: 3♂, 1♀, Israel: Mt. Hermon, 1600 m, 5.IX.1981, A. Freidberg [TAU].

Distribution: Type locality: Egypt: Baharia Oasis. Palaeartic: Egypt, Israel. New for Israel. First record after description.

Asyndetus longicornis Negrobov, 1973: 160.

Material examined: 1♂, 1♀, [Uzbekistan: upper stream of Syr Darya River:] “Сыр Дарья” [ZIN]. 2♂, 1♀, [Kazakhstan: Kosaral:] “Косараль” /24 [ZIN]; 1♂, [Tajikistan or Uzbekistan: Zeravshan Valley:] “Заравш. д.” /1 [ZIN]; 1♂, Russia: Astrakhan Region, Ikryanoe district, Zyuzino, 45.751°N, 47.678°E, 8–9.V.2010, water, pastures, K. Tomkovich [ZMU].

Additional material examined: 1♀, [Tajikistan or Uzbekistan: Zeravshan Valley:] “Заравш. д.” /6 [ZIN]; 2♀, [Uzbekistan: Keles:] “Келесь” /22 [ZIN]; 2♀, [Uzbekistan: Karak:] “Каракъ” /7 [ZIN]; 1♀, [Kazakhstan:] Taldyqorghon Region, Katutau Mts., Kuibynskoe Gorge, 25 km NWN Koktal, 30.VI.1988, Tanasiichuk [ZIN]; 1♀, [Turkmenistan:] 30 km E Nebit-Dag, S slope of Bolshoi Balkhan Ridge, 9.V.1984, Tanasiichuk [ZIN].

Remarks: *A. longicornis* males examined show some extent of variation in shape of antennal postpedicel (with ovate to subtriangular apex) and setation of phallus (aedeagus); the characters were considered diagnostic by Pârvu (1989) when he described his new species *A. negrobovi* from Romania. E.g., two males collected in Kosaral differ from each other in subapical setation of phallus (in addition to shape of postpedicel): weaker (as shown by Negrobov, 1973: Fig. 24) or stronger dorsal setation with two basal dents long and narrow (as shown by Pârvu, 1989: Fig. 5). Therefore, *A. longicornis* can repre-

sent a complex of widely distributed sibling species (including *A. negrobovi*) or different phenotypes of the same species.

Distribution: Type locality: “Mongolei, Südgobi aimak, 40 km SSO von Nomagon, Salzbodenwiese, in der Nähe von der Wasserquelle”. Palaeartic: China (Inner Mongolia), Hungary, Kazakhstan, Mongolia, ?Romania, Russia (Astrakhan), Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan. New for Kazakhstan, Russia, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan.

Asyndetus mixtus Negrobov et Shamshev, 1986: 48.

Material examined: 1♂ (with broken abdomen), [Tajikistan or Uzbekistan: Zeravshan Valley:] “Заравш. д.” /4. / “*albipalpus* Lw.” [old hand-written museum label] / “*Asyndetus albipalpis* Lw., Stackelberg det.” (ZIN); 1♂, [Tajikistan or Uzbekistan: Zeravshan Valley:] “Заравш. д.” /28 (ZIN); 1♂, [Tajikistan: Vorukh:] “Ворухъ / 20” (ZIN).

Remarks: Negrobov & Shamshev (1986) referred the type locality of the species in error to Turkmenistan instead of Uzbekistan.

Distribution: Type locality: [Uzbekistan]: Samarkand, Kattakurgan district, Kumak. Palaeartic: Tajikistan, Uzbekistan. New for Tajikistan.

Asyndetus separatus (Becker), 1902: 56 (*Meringopherusa*); Becker, 1918: 78 (*Asyndetus*); Negrobov, 1973: 161.

Asyndetus lateinterruptus Strobl, in Czerny, Strobl, 1909: 190 (as *late-interruptus*). Type locality: Italy and Austria: “Monfalcone bei Triest; Admont” (synonymised by Becker, 1918: 78)

Material examined: 1♂, [Egypt:] Fayūm, III, 44741 / *Meringopherusa separata* Beck., det. Becker [ZIN]; 1♀, [Egypt:] Kairo, XI, 44277 [ZIN]; 3♂: Cyprus, Famagusta, 9–12.VII.1939 (Håkan Lindb.) [ZMH]; 3♀, Israel: Ein Hajla, 11.V.1977, A. Freidberg [TAU].

Remarks: A male from Fayūm (Egypt) examined may belong to the type series of *A. separatus*. It corresponds to the description and figure provided by Becker (1902). The male genitalia preparation was made by the author of this paper, showing its strong similarity with the *A. pseudoseparatus* described in this paper (see Fig. 1), but differing from the figure provided by Negrobov (1973) in shape of epandrial lobe and in simple phallus (without setation). In addition, a male from Fayūm has two pedunculate apical setae on the left epandrial lobe and three apical setae (of which one seta is pedunculate) on the right epandrial lobe. Negrobov (1973) studied the material collected from Tajikistan, and his pictures may belong to another species.

Distribution: Type locality: Egypt: Alexandrien, Fayūm. Palaeartic: Algeria, Cyprus, Egypt, Greece, Iraq, Israel, Libya, Spain, Tunisia, ?Tajikistan. New for Israel.

Asyndetus thaicus Grootaert et Meuffels, 2002: 42; Wang et al., 2007: 151.

Material examined: 2♂, India: Gujarat, Naliya, env. Kothara, riv. Nayera, 23.137°N, 68.931°E, 5.X.2012, K. Tomkovich [ZMU]; 1♂, 2♀, India: Goa, Palolem, ~15.018°N, 74.018°E, 3–9.II.2009, K. Tomkovich [ZMU].

Remarks: This is the second *Asyndetus* species found in India, which is still undercollected. The wide areas of *A. latifrons* and *A. thaicus* distribution assume the presence of more Oriental, Palaeartic and Afrotropical species of the genus in this country.

Distribution: Type locality: Thailand: Rayong Province, Ko Samed, Tarn Tawan. Oriental: China (Yunnan), India (Goa, Gujarat), Thailand. New for India.

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